

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: SEO****FIRST NAME: JUNG NAHYUN****PROGRAM CODE: DME****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 06****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is 3%

The author used the following software: MSWord Microsoft 365 on Windows 11

QUIZ FOR KEY CONCEPTS IN ACA-401D

1. Which style guide does the EU Commission recommend for uniformity in official documents?
 - APA
 - Chicago Manual of Style
 - European Commission Style Guide¹**
 - MLA
2. What is the primary purpose of the dissertation concept paper, as discussed by Sampson?
 - To finalize research findings
 - To gather preliminary data

¹ European Commission, *English style guide: A handbook for authors and translators in the European Commission*, 8th ed. (European Union, 2021), 1-2.

- **To frame the research and involve the supervisory committee early²**
 - To explore alternative research methods
- 3. According to Turabian, which citation style is commonly used in humanities?
 - APA
 - **Notes-Bibliography³**
 - Author-Date
 - IEEE
- 4. What is a critical reason for citing sources, as highlighted in Turabian's manual?
 - To avoid legal disputes
 - To add visual appeal to documents
 - **To acknowledge original ideas and promote intellectual integrity⁴**
 - To lengthen the bibliography section
- 5. Which punctuation mark does the European Commission Style Guide recommend for linking related independent clauses?
 - Comma
 - Colon
 - Dash
 - **Semicolon⁵**
- 6. In qualitative research, which concept refers to a researcher's ongoing reflection on how their background influences the study?

² James P. Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 2nd ed. (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 2-7.

³ Kate L. Turabian, Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, and William T. FitzGerald, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 9th ed. (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 141-142.

⁴ *Ibid.*, 139-141.

⁵ European Commission, *English Style Guide*, 9.

- Positionality
 - **Reflexivity**⁶
 - Member Checking
 - Ethical Clearance
7. Which element is crucial for ensuring data integrity in health sector reports, according to Turabian?
- Consistent font size
 - **Ethical data presentation**⁷
 - Summative visuals only
 - Word count limitations
8. What does the European Commission Style Guide recommend regarding the use of abbreviations?
- Avoid abbreviations altogether
 - Use abbreviations without defining them
 - **Define abbreviations upon first use and maintain consistency**⁸
 - Define only complex abbreviations
9. According to Sampson, which method allows for a holistic understanding of complex research questions by combining strengths of qualitative and quantitative methods?
- Ethnographic research
 - **Mixed-Methods Approach**⁹
 - Literature Review

⁶ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation*, 4th ed. (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, Inc., 2019), 151-153.

⁷ Turabian, *Manual for Writers*, 80-82.

⁸ European Commission, *English Style Guide*, 41-42.

⁹ Sampson, *Guide to Dissertation Research*, 34-49.

- Meta-Analysis
10. Which term describes subtle daily acts of defiance that resist colonial power, as discussed in the study material?
- Legal resistance
 - Revolutionary resistance
 - Everyday resistance¹⁰**
 - Passive observation

BIBLIOGRAPHY

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¹⁰ Maysa Shqerat, "Everyday Resistance and Settler Colonialism in Palestine" (PhD diss., University of Sussex, 2018), 65.

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